

Mechanism of Oxidation of Thiosemicarbazide by Acid Bromate in Aqueous and Partial Aqueous Media : A Kinetic Study

B. THIMME GOWDA*, V. PARDHASARADHI and A. CHITHARANJAN HEGDE

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 30 December 1991, revised 21 September 1992, accepted 2 December 1992

The kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide (TSC) by potassium bromate have been studied in aqueous perchloric acid and water-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) media. The rate shows first order kinetics in [oxidant] and positive dependence in $[H^+]$ in both the media. It exhibits fractional and first order kinetics in [TSC] in aqueous and water-acetic acid media, respectively. Addition of KBr has little effect on the rates. Increase in ionic strength of the medium decreases the rate while increase in acetic acid composition of the solvent increases the rate. The mechanisms consistent with the observed results have been discussed. The validity of the rate laws is also tested by recalculating the rate constants as [TSC] and $[H^+]$ are varied.

The chemistry of hydrazine derivatives is of importance due to their wide synthetic and analytical applications and biological activities¹. Thiosemicarbazide ($H_2NHNCSNH_2$, abbreviated as TSC) is the simplest hydrazine derivative of thio-carbamic acid. The chemical behaviour of thiosemicarbazide is similar to its keto analogue semicarbazide. However, greater chemical versatility of the thione group compared with that of the keto group is responsible for the more varied behaviour of TSC. Although TSC has been extensively used in synthetic organic chemistry and as a metal chelating agent², there are no report except our recent work³, on the mechanistic aspects of its reactions in solution. In an effort to provide insight into the mechanism of its activity in solution, we report herein the oxidation kinetics of thiosemicarbazide with acid bromate in aqueous and water-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) media. The chemistry of bromate ion in aqueous acid medium is also of considerable interest due to its importance in the mechanistic chemistry⁴.

Results and Discussion

In aqueous medium: At fixed $[HClO_4]$ with multiple excess of [TSC], the plots of $\log [KBrO_3]_0/[KBrO_3]$ versus time were linear for over two half-lives and the pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots were unaffected by the changes in $[KBrO_3]$, thereby establishing first order kinetics in $[KBrO_3]$. The rate increased with increase in [TSC] with fractional order kinetics (Table 1). The double reciprocal plot of k_{obs} vs $1/[TSC]$ was linear (Fig. 1). At fixed $[KBrO_3]$ and [TSC], the rate showed positive dependence in $[HClO_4]$. These results and the observed non-influence of added reduced product of the oxidant on the rate (Table 2) may be explained by a Michaelis-Menten type mechanism shown in

Scheme 1. The active species in this mechanism is $H_2BrO_3^+$, as reported in the literature⁴.

Scheme 1

Based on Scheme 1, the rate laws (1-4) have been deduced.

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt} &= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{oxidant}]_{\text{tot}} [\text{TSC}] [H^+]^2 [H_2O]}{\{1 + K_1 [H^+]^2\} [H_2O] + K_1 K_2 [\text{TSC}] [H^+]^2} \\ &= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{oxidant}]_{\text{tot}} [\text{TSC}] [H^+]^2}{1 + K_1 [H^+]^2 + K_1 K_2' [\text{TSC}] [H^+]^2} \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

where $K_2' = K_2/[H_2O]$

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{TSC}] [H^+]^2}{1 + K_1 [H^+]^2 + K_1 K_2' [\text{TSC}] [H^+]^2} \quad (2)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1 + K_1 [H^+]^2}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [H^+]^2} \frac{1}{[\text{TSC}]} + \frac{1}{k_3 [H_2O]} \quad (3)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{TSC}]} \frac{1}{[H^+]^2} + \frac{1 + K_2' [\text{TSC}]}{K_2 k_3 [\text{TSC}]} \quad (4)$$

The rate laws (3 and 4) are consistent with the observed linearities between $1/k_{obs}$ and $1/[\text{TSC}]$ (Fig. 1) and $1/k_{obs}$ and $1/[H^+]^2$ (figure not shown) with finite intercepts on the ordinates. The constant k_3 was calculated from the intercept of the plot,

*Present Address : Humboldt Research Fellow, Institut fur Physikal Chemie III, Technische Hochschule, Petersenstr. 20, D-6100, Darmstadt, Germany.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (TSC) BY POTASSIUM BROMATE IN AQUEOUS (AT 303 K) AND WATER ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) (AT 293 K) MEDIA IN THE PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID ($\mu = 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)

Aqueous medium					H ₂ O-HOAc (1 : 1, v/v)				
$10^3[\text{KBrO}_3]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{TSC}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	pH ^a	$10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹	$10^3[\text{KBrO}_3]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{TSC}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2[\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	pH ^a	$10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹
[Oxidant] ₀ variation									
0.5	1.0	3.0	1.55	5.7	0.2	1.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	14.2 (13.0)
1.0	1.0	3.0	1.55	5.8	0.5	1.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	14.1 (12.7)
2.0	1.0	3.0	1.55	5.6	1.0	1.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	13.9 (11.6)
—	—	—	—	—	2.0	1.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	13.3 (10.7)
[Substrate] ₀ variation									
1.0	0.5	3.0	1.55	3.6	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	1.0	3.0	1.55	5.8	1.0	0.5	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	6.8 (5.7)
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.55	8.6	1.0	1.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	13.9 (11.6)
1.0	3.0	3.0	1.55	10.2	1.0	2.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	28.6 (24.8)
1.0	5.0	3.0	1.55	12.9	1.0	4.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	53.7 (44.8)
1.0	7.0	3.0	1.55	15.1	—	—	—	—	—
[Acid] variation									
1.0	1.0	1.0	2.02	1.6	1.0	1.0	1.0 (0.1)	2.43 (2.60)	12.4 (11.2)
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.72	3.7	1.0	1.0	2.0 (0.2)	2.32 (2.59)	13.9 (11.6)
1.0	1.0	3.0	1.55	5.8	1.0	1.0	3.0 (0.5)	2.22 (2.56)	15.7 (11.8)
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.34	8.1	1.0	1.0	5.0 (1.0)	2.14 (2.43)	17.9 (12.4)
1.0	1.0	7.0	1.20	10.5	1.0	1.0	7.0 (—)	2.04 (—)	19.5 (—)

^aMeasured values at different [HClO₄].

$1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{TSC}]$, by inserting $[\text{H}_2\text{O}] = 55.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Further, $[\text{TSC}]$ was varied at different temperatures (298–313 K) and the values of k_3 were calculated at each temperature; $10^5 k_3$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) = 2.12, 3.13, 5.15 and 8.01 at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K respectively. The activation parameters were then calculated from the plots of $\log k_3$ vs $1/T$ (Table 2).

the two sets of values checks the consistency of the rate law and provides support to the suggested mechanism.

In water-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) medium: Oxidation in aqueous acetic acid showed slightly different kinetics. The rate exhibited first order dependence each in $[\text{oxidant}]$ and $[\text{TSC}]$, and fractional order in $[\text{H}^+]$ as compared to kinetics

 TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION, ADDITION OF KBr ON THE RATES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF TSC BY POTASSIUM BROMATE IN AQUEOUS (AT 303 K) (I) AND H₂O-HOAc (AT 293 K) (II) MEDIA

μ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)		HOAc %	$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹) (II)	[KBr] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)		Activation parameters		
	(I)	(II)				(I)	(II)			(I)
0.10	6.6	15.1	25	2.3	0	5.8	13.9	E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	70.1	50.8
0.20	5.0	13.9	50	13.9	0.01	—	14.5	log A	7.6	6.2
0.30	4.4	9.7	65	36.6	0.02	5.4	—	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	65.2	49.4
0.50	3.9	5.3	—	—	0.04	5.3	16.2	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹)	-116.2	-130.9
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	100.4	87.8

$10^3[\text{KBrO}_3]_0 = 10^2[\text{TSC}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The equilibrium constant K_2 was calculated from the intercept, $\{1 + K_2[\text{TSC}]\}/K_2 k_3 [\text{TSC}]$ of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ plot by inserting k_3 , $[\text{TSC}]$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ values, $K_2 = 1.82 \times 10^4$. The constant K_1 was calculated from the slope of either of the two plots by inserting K_2 , k_3 and $[\text{H}^+]$ or $[\text{TSC}]$ values; K_1 ($\text{dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2}$) = 245.

The computed constants K_1 , K_2 and k_3 were employed to verify the rate constants from the rate law (3) or (4) as $[\text{TSC}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ were varied. The recalculated values compared with the experimental rate constants (k_{obs}) are shown in Table 3. A reasonably good agreement between

observed in aqueous medium. The rate decreased with increase in ionic strength of the medium, while it increased with increase in acetic acid concentration of the medium. Addition of KBr had no effect on the rate. The reaction in aqueous acetic acid was carried out in the presence of 0.20 mol dm⁻³ sodium acetate. Hence under these conditions, effective $[\text{H}^+]$ would be much smaller than that in aqueous medium, for comparable $[\text{HClO}_4]$. Therefore assuming HBrO_3 to be the reactive species, the following scheme explains the observed results.

Fig. 1 (i) Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[TSC]$ in aqueous medium; $10^3[KBrO_3]_0=33.33$, $[HClO_4]=1.0$ mol dm⁻³, temp.=303 K. (ii) Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$ in H₂O-HOAc (1 : 1, v/v) medium; $10^3[KBrO_3]_0=10^2[TSC]_0=1.0$ mol dm⁻³, temp.=293 K.

The rate laws (6 and 7) predict linearities between k_{obs} and $[TSC]$ at constant $[H^+]$, and between $1/k_{obs}$ and $1/[H^+]$ at constant $[TSC]$. The plots of k_{obs} vs $[TSC]$ at constant $[H^+]$ and $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$ at constant $[TSC]$ (Fig. 1) were linear, in conformity with the predictions. The ratio of intercept to slope of the latter plot gave K_4 (dm³ mol⁻¹)=175. k_s was calculated from the intercept of the plot by inserting $[TSC]$; k_s (dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹)=0.30.

The effects of solvent composition on the rates of ion-ion; ion-dipolar molecule and dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule reactions have been described elsewhere^{5,6}. The observed dielectric effect (Table 2) and increase of rate with decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium, are in conformity with Amis⁵ and other concepts⁶, and the suggested mechanisms.

Relatively high positive values of free energy of activation may signal bond-breaking in the formation of transition state. Larger negative values of the entropy of activation indicate that the more ordered activated complexes are formed.

Experimental

Analytical grade potassium bromate was used and its aqueous solution standardised just before use. Thiosemicarbazide (E. Merck) was purified

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF RECALCULATED CONSTANTS AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUES AS $[TSC]$ AND $[HClO_4]$ ARE VARIED FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE BY POTASSIUM BROMATE IN AQUEOUS AND AQUO-ACETIC ACID MEDIA

$10^2[TSC]$ mol dm ⁻³	10^4k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)				$10^2[HClO_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	10^4k_{obs} (s ⁻¹) ⁻¹	
	Aqueous		H ₂ O-HOAc			Aqueous	
	Recalc.	Expt.	Recalc.	Expt.		Recalc.	Expt.
0.5	3.7	3.6	7.0	6.8	1.0	1.2	1.6
1.0	6.1	5.8	14.0	13.9	2.0	3.7	3.7
2.0	9.0	8.6	28.1	28.6	3.0	6.1	5.8
4.0	—	—	56.1	53.7	5.0	9.2	8.1
5.0	12.5	12.9	—	—	7.0	10.8	10.5

Scheme 2

The rate laws (5–7) are in accordance with Scheme 2.

$$\frac{d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt} = \frac{K_4 k_s [\text{oxidant}]_{tot} [TSC] [H^+]}{1 + K_4 [H^+]} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or} \quad k_{obs} = \frac{K_4 k_s [TSC] [H^+]}{1 + K_4 [H^+]} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \left\{ \frac{1}{K_4 [H^+]} + 1 \right\} \frac{1}{k_s [TSC]} \quad (7)$$

by recrystallisation from hot water, and its aqueous stock solution (0.10 mol dm⁻³) was employed.

Kinetic measurement: The kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with $[TSC] \gg [\text{oxidant}]$. The reaction was initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solutions containing known amounts of TSC (0.005–0.070 mol dm⁻³), HClO₄ (0.001–0.070 mol dm⁻³), and water (and acetic acid to maintain 1 : 1, v/v water-acetic acid) thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored for at least two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of unreacted bromate at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were

computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$ error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of bromate-TSC was determined by equilibrating varying ratios of TSC and bromate in aqueous and water-acetic acid media. TSC was found to get oxidised to sulphate to an extent of about $92 \pm 4\%$. The 3 : 4 molar stoichiometry observed may be represented by equation,

The other products of oxidation were identified by standard tests⁷.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.P.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. F. DUUS, in "Comprehensive Organic Chemistry" eds. S. R. BARTON and W. D. OLLIS, Pergamon, Oxford, 1979, Vol. 3, p. 442 and references therein.
2. M. J. M. CAMPBELL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, **15**, 279.
3. B. T. GOWDA and J. I. BHAT, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 2119; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 597, 786, 974; 1989, **28**, 211; B. T. GOWDA and R. V. RAO, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1988, 355; B. T. GOWDA and B. S. SHERIGARA, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1989, **21**, 31; B. T. GOWDA and V. PARDHASARADHI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Chem. Sci.*, 1990, **102**, 463.
4. H. A. YOUNG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3310; VIBHA AVASTHI and A. C. CHATTERJI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1970, **245**, 154, 161; 1972, **249**, 17; R. NATARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1969, **57**, 5021; *Tetrahedron*, 1974, **30**, 2785; *IJCK*, 1976, **8**, 205; P. N. CHAR, S. SONDU, B. SETHURAM and T. N. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 31; 1989, **28**, 670; CH. S. REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 911; N. KRISHNAMURTHY, CH. S. REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 288; S. B. JONNALAGADDA, R. H. SIMOYI and G. K. MUTHAKIA *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1988, 1111.
5. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966.
6. S. G. ENTELIS and R. P. TIGER, "Reaction Kinetics in the Liquid Phase", Wiley, New York, 1976; P. ZUMAN and R. C. PATEL, "Techniques in Organic Reaction Kinetics", Wiley, New York, 1984; K. J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", Harper and Row, New York, 1987.
7. "Vogel's Text Book of Macro and Semimicro Qualitative Inorganic Analysis", ed. G. SUEHLA, Orient Longman, New Delhi, 1982.